

On Main Operators In Nonlinear Differential Games With Fixed Time

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Abstract.

In the present article we study some approximation properties of the main operators (upper and lower operators) and on the basis of these properties a connection between the upper and lower operators in nonlinear differential games and its applications to the problem of pursuit are established.

Keywords: differential games, admissible control, approximation, pursuer, evader, strategy.

1 Introduction

The structure of nonlinear differential games is described by operators T^t and $\prod^t$, [1,2] as natural generalization of the concept of alternating integral for linear differential games [3-5]. Publications [6-22] deal with further development of operator structures in nonlinear differential games. In particular, lower analogues operators T^t and $\prod^t$ and their applications to study of qualitative structure of phase space of differential games of pursuit-evasion were suggested in [10-13]. Questions of approximation of the operators T^t and $\prod^t$ by simpler operators were studied in [6,11]. In the future, for the symmetry operators T^t and $\prod^t$ are said to be the upper, and their lower analogues T_t and $\prod_t$ call lower operators in nonlinear differential games. In the present article we study some approximation properties of the operators $\prod^t$ and $\prod_t$ (upper and lower operators) and on the basis of these properties a connection between the upper and lower operators in nonlinear differential games and its applications to the problem of pursuit are established. Let $K(R^d)$ (respectively $C(R^d)$) be family of all nonempty compact (closed) subsets of R^d , $H = \{z \in R^d; |z| \leq 1\}$ be closed unit ball in R^d ; $\omega = \{\tau_0, \tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n\}$ be partition of segment $[0, t]$ ($0 = \tau_0 < \tau_1 < \tau_2 < \dots < \tau_n = t$, n may depend on ω); Let us assume $r\Delta_i = |\tau_i - \tau_{i-1}|$, and $|\omega| = t$, ω is a partition of the segment $[0, t]$. If X is subset of the Euclidean space, Δ is segment in R , then by $X[\Delta]$ denote the set of all measurable functions $a(\cdot) : \Delta \rightarrow X$. When $\Delta = [\alpha, \beta]$, we simply write $X[\alpha, \beta]$.

Let us consider the differential game

$$\frac{dz}{dt} = f(z, u, v), \quad (1)$$

where $z \in R^d$, $u \in P$, $v \in Q$ and $f : R^d \times P \times Q \rightarrow R^d$, $P \in K(R^p)$, $Q \in K(R^q)$. Along with the system (1) we also fix the set of M , $M \subset R^d$, which is called terminal set.

We suppose that further the function f holds the following conditions.

A. The function $f : R^d \times P \times Q \rightarrow R^d$ is continuous and is locally the Lipschitz type by z (i.e. the function f holds the Lipschitz condition on every compact set $D \in K(R^d)$ with the constant L_D , depending on compact D).

B. There is a constant $C \geq 0$, such that for all $z \in R^d$, $u \in P$, $v \in Q$, the inequality

$$|z \cdot f(z, u, v)| \leq C(1 + |z|^2)$$

holds.

C. The set $f(z, P, v)$ is convex for all $z \in R^d$, $v \in Q$, and the set $f(z, u, Q)$ is convex for all $z \in R^d$, $u \in P$.

We call every function $u(\cdot) \in P[\alpha, \beta]$ (respectively $v(\cdot) \in Q[\alpha, \beta]$) as admissible control of pursuer (respectively evader). We denote by $z(t, u(\cdot), v(\cdot), \xi)$ solution of the

system (1), which corresponds to admissible control $u(t)$ and $v(t)$ and initial point $\xi \in R^d$ (precisely definition of a trajectory is given in Section 4). Pursuit starts from a point $z_0 \in R^d \setminus M$ and it is considered to be ended, when the phase point hits the set M . In other words, pursuer aims to realize the inclusion $z(\tau) \in M$. Then, we say that pursuit from a point z_0 is completed at the time τ in the game (1). Naturally, there is a question: *From which initial points z_0 pursuit can be completed at the time τ in the game (1)?* To solve this problem L.S. Pontryagin has introduced the second method of pursuit in a linear differential game. The second method of pursuit is formulated in terms of alternating integral [3-5]. Solution of this problem for nonlinear differential games is described by operators T^t and Π^t , [1,2] as natural generalization of the concept of alternating integral for linear differential games. In the present article, the basic definitions and results are presented in relation to operators Π^t and Π_t .

Definition 1. The operator Π^ε associates every set $A \subset R^d$ with the set $\Pi^\varepsilon A$ of all points $\xi \in R^d$, such that for any admissible control of evader $v(\cdot) \in Q[0, \varepsilon]$ there is admissible control $u(\cdot) \in P[0, \varepsilon]$ of pursuer, such that the corresponding trajectory $z(t, u(\cdot), v(\cdot), \xi)$ with beginning at the initial point $\xi \in R^d$ hits $A \subset R^d$ at time ε , i.e. $z(\varepsilon) \in A$.

Definition 2. The operator Π_ε associates every set $A \subset R^d$ with the set $\Pi_\varepsilon A$ of all points $\xi \in R^d$, such that there is admissible control pursuer $u(\cdot) \in P[0, \varepsilon]$ for any admissible control of evader $v(\cdot) \in Q[0, \varepsilon]$, moreover, corresponding trajectory $z(t, u(\cdot), v(\cdot), \xi)$ with the beginning at the point $\xi \in R^d$ hits $A \subset R^d$ at time ε , i.e. $z(\varepsilon) \in A$.

By means of operations of association and intersection we can write operators Π^ε and Π_ε as follows:

$$\Pi^\varepsilon A = \bigcap_{v(\cdot) \in Q[0, \varepsilon]} \bigcup_{u(\cdot) \in P[0, \varepsilon]} \{ \xi \in R^d \mid z(\varepsilon, u(\cdot), v(\cdot), \xi) \in A \}, \quad (2)$$

$$\Pi_\varepsilon A = \bigcup_{u(\cdot) \in P[0, \varepsilon]} \bigcap_{v(\cdot) \in Q[0, \varepsilon]} \{ \xi \in R^d \mid z(\varepsilon, u(\cdot), v(\cdot), \xi) \in A \}. \quad (3)$$

Let $\omega = \{ \tau_0, \tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n \}$ be partition of segment $[0, t]$. We assume

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi^\omega M &= \Pi^{\delta_1} \Pi^{\delta_2} \dots \Pi^{\delta_n} M, \\ \Pi_\omega M &= \Pi_{\delta_1} \Pi_{\delta_2} \dots \Pi_{\delta_n} M, \end{aligned}$$

where $\delta_i = \tau_i - \tau_{i-1}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Definition 3. Let $\Pi^t M = \bigcap_{|\omega|=t} \Pi^\omega M, \Pi_t M = \bigcup_{|\omega|=t} \Pi_\omega M$.

$\Pi^t M$ (respectively $\Pi_t M$) is called the upper (lower) operator of nonlinear differential games with fixed time [2-15].

Further, if it will be necessary, we shall indicate in notations the dependence of operators not only of ω or t , but also of other initial data, e.g. $\Pi_\varepsilon(M, P, Q), \Pi^\varepsilon(M, P, Q)$.

A concepts of the upper and lower operators have the following role in nonlinear differential games: From points z_0 with $z_0 \in \Pi^t M$ (respectively $z_0 \in \Pi_t M$) the pursuit can be completed at the time τ with (without) discriminating against the evader controls [1-13].

2 Preliminaries

For completeness we state certain properties of the operators Π^ε and Π_ε . We note that for arbitrary family X_λ the following inclusions take place

$$\Pi^\varepsilon \bigcap_\lambda X_\lambda \subset \bigcap_\lambda \Pi^\varepsilon X_\lambda, \quad \bigcup_\lambda \Pi_\varepsilon X_\lambda \subset \Pi_\varepsilon \bigcup_\lambda X_\lambda. \quad (4)$$

Lemma 1 [6, 12]. Let $X_\lambda \in C(R^d)$ be non increasing (nondecreasing) direction of closed (open) sets. Then the equality $\Pi^\varepsilon \bigcap_\lambda X_\lambda = \bigcap_\lambda \Pi^\varepsilon X_\lambda$ ($\bigcup_\lambda \Pi_\varepsilon X_\lambda = \Pi_\varepsilon \bigcup_\lambda X_\lambda$) is valid.

Lemma 2 [6, 12]. The following relations

- a) $\Pi^{\varepsilon_1} \Pi^{\varepsilon_2} M \subset \Pi^{\varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2} M$, $\Pi_{\varepsilon_1} \Pi_{\varepsilon_2} M \supset \Pi_{\varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2} M$.
 б) for any $|\omega_1| = t$, $|\omega_2| = t$ and $\omega_1 \subset \omega_2$, $\Pi^{\omega_2} M \subset \Pi^{\omega_1} M$,
 $\Pi^{\omega_1} M \subset \Pi^{\omega_2} M$, are valid.

It were shown in [6,12] that 1) If $M \in C(R^d)$, then

$$\Pi^t M = \bigcap_{\delta > 0} \Pi^t(M + \delta H);$$

2) if M is open subset of R^d , then

$$\Pi_t M = \bigcup_{\delta > 0} \Pi_t(M * \delta H).$$

Let operator A^ε (correspondingly A_ε) differs from the operator Π^ε (correspondingly from Π_ε) by the property that in Definitions 1 (correspondingly in Definition 2), only constant controls $v(\cdot) = v \in Q$ (correspondingly $u(\cdot) = u \in P$) are taken instead of arbitrary admissible controls $v(\cdot) \in Q[0, \varepsilon]$ (correspondingly $u(\cdot) \in P[0, \varepsilon]$).

Let $\omega = \{\tau_0, \tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n\}$ be partition of segment $[0, t]$. We assume

$$A^\omega M = A^{\delta_1} A^{\delta_2} \dots A^{\delta_n} M,$$

$$A_\omega M = A_{\delta_1} A_{\delta_2} \dots A_{\delta_n} M,$$

where $\delta_i = \tau_i - \tau_{i-1}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Definition 4. $A^t M = \bigcap_{|\omega|=t} A^\omega M$, $A_t M = \bigcup_{|\omega|=t} A_\omega M$.

Theorem 1 [6, 17]. We have the equality

$$\Pi^t M = A^t M \tag{5}$$

for $M \in C(R^d)$ and if M is open subset of R^d , then

$$\Pi_t M = A_t M. \tag{6}$$

Lemma 3 [6, 17]. Let ω_k be infinitely reducing sequence of partitions of the segment $[0, t]$, i. e., $\omega_k \subset \omega_{k+1}$, $|\omega_k| = t$, $\max |\tau_i^k - \tau_{i-1}^k| \rightarrow 0$ for $k \rightarrow \infty$. Then the following equality holds

$$\Pi^t M = \bigcap_{k \geq 1} \Pi^{\omega_k} M$$

for closed M and

$$\Pi_t M = \bigcup_{k \geq 1} \Pi_{\omega_k} M$$

for open M .

3 Approximation of the main operators

For nonlinear problems pursuit the construction of operators $\Pi^t M$ and $\Pi_t M$ is a lot of difficulties. Therefore the problem of working out effective schemes for the construction of these operators is relevant.

Consider the following operators accordingly

$$\Theta^\varepsilon B = \bigcap_{v \in Q} \bigcup_{u \in P} \{ \xi \in R^d \mid z(\varepsilon, u, v, \xi) = \xi + \varepsilon f(\xi, u, v) \in B, \}$$

$$\Theta_\varepsilon B = \bigcup_{u \in P} \bigcap_{v \in Q} \{ \xi \in R^d \mid z(\varepsilon, u, v, \xi) = \xi + \varepsilon f(\xi, u, v) \in B. \}$$

Definition operators Θ^t and Θ_t are similar to definition Π^t and Π_t respectively.

In this paper we consider the problem of approximation operators $\Pi^t M$ and $\Pi_t M$ by means of iteration of operators Θ^ε and Θ_ε , respectively. On the basis of these properties a connection between the operators $\Pi^t M$ and $\Pi_t M$ in nonlinear differential games and its applications to the problem of pursuit are established.

In what follows, we will assume that the boundary of M (∂M) is compact. We denote by D_* the set of all points of $\xi \in R^d$, of which it is possible to achieve the set ∂M (the boundary of M) at the appropriate admissible controls $u(\cdot)$ and $v(\cdot)$ for a time not exceeding θ . Let $D = D_* + H$ and constant is the quantity that can depend only on the function f , sets P, Q, D . We shall suppose that $t \leq \theta$. Condition B guarantees boundedness of the set D [16]. We assume $K = \max\{ \| f(z, u, v) \| \mid z \in D, u \in P, v \in Q \}$.

Lemma 4. There exists a positive number L such that the following inclusions

$$A^\varepsilon M \subset \Theta^\varepsilon(M + L\varepsilon^2 H) \subset A^\varepsilon(M + 2L\varepsilon^2 H), \quad (7)$$

$$A_\varepsilon(M \underline{*} 2L\varepsilon^2 H) \subset \Theta_\varepsilon(M \underline{*} L\varepsilon^2 H) \subset A_\varepsilon M \quad (8)$$

hold (see[4] about operators $+$ and $\underline{*}$).

The proofs are analogous, so we confine ourselves to the proof of (8). Let ξ be arbitrary element from the set $A_\varepsilon(M \underline{*} 2L\varepsilon^2 H)$. Then, there exists an admissible control of pursuer $u \in P$, such that for any admissible control evader $v(\cdot) \in Q[0, \varepsilon]$, the corresponding trajectory $z(t, u, v(\cdot), \xi)$ with the initial point of $\xi \in R^d$ hits $M \underline{*} 2L\varepsilon^2 H$ at time ε i.e. $z(\varepsilon) \in M \underline{*} 2L\varepsilon^2 H$. Therefore

$$z(\varepsilon, u, v(\cdot), \xi) = \xi + \int_0^\varepsilon f(z(t), u, v(t)) dt \in M \underline{*} 2L\varepsilon^2 H. \quad (9)$$

In virtue of the condition A for arbitrary controls $u \in P, v(\cdot) \in Q$ and the initial point $\xi \in R^d$ we have the relation

$$| f(z(t), u, v(t)) - f(\xi, u, v(t)) | \leq L_1 | z(t) - \xi |. \quad (10)$$

On the other hand,

$$| z(t, u, v(t), \xi) - \xi | \leq K\varepsilon, t \in [0, \varepsilon]. \quad (11)$$

Hence, using the inequality (10), we obtain

$$| f(z(t), u, v(t)) - f(\xi, u, v(t)) | \leq L\varepsilon, \quad (12)$$

where $L = L_1 K$.

Let us prove now that for every $v(\cdot) \in Q[0, \varepsilon]$, there is constant control $v \in Q$, for which the equality

$$\xi + \int_0^\varepsilon f(\xi, u, v(t)) dt = \xi + \varepsilon f(\xi, u, v), \quad (13)$$

take place.

Due to the condition C, the set $f(\xi, u, Q)$ is convex for every $u \in P$. Therefore we have

$$\int_0^\varepsilon f(\xi, u, v(t))dt \in \varepsilon f(\xi, u, Q).$$

It follows that there is a $v \in Q$ such that

$$\int_0^\varepsilon f(\xi, u, v(t))dt = \varepsilon f(\xi, u, v).$$

Consequently, for any $v(\cdot) \in Q[0, \varepsilon]$ there is a constant control $v \in Q$, for which the equality

$$\xi + \int_0^\varepsilon f(\xi, u, v(t))dt = \xi + \varepsilon f(\xi, u, v)$$

holds. Applying inequality (12) to the right side of the equality (13), we obtain

$$\xi + \varepsilon f(\xi, u, v) \in \xi + \int_0^\varepsilon f(z(t), u, v(t))dt + L\varepsilon^2 H. \quad (14)$$

Using the inclusion (9), we have

$$\xi + \varepsilon f(\xi, u, v) \in M_* 2L\varepsilon^2 H + L\varepsilon^2 H.$$

Hence,

$$\xi \in \Theta_\varepsilon(M_* L\varepsilon^2 H).$$

Similarly, the right side of the turn proved (8). Proof of the inclusion (7) is similar to proof of the relation (8).

Lemma 5. The following inclusions are valid

$$\Theta^\varepsilon(M) + L\delta^2 H \subset \Theta^\varepsilon(M + L\delta^2(1 + L_1\varepsilon)H). \quad (15)$$

$$\Theta_\varepsilon(M_* L\delta^2(1 + L_1\varepsilon)H) + L\delta^2 H \subset \Theta_\varepsilon M. \quad (16)$$

Proof. Let η be an arbitrary element of the left side inclusion (15). Then there is $\xi \in \Theta^\varepsilon(M)$ such that

$$|\eta - \xi| \leq L\delta^2. \quad (17)$$

By virtue of the condition A we have

$$|f(\xi, u, v) - f(\eta, u, v)| \leq L_1 |\eta - \xi|. \quad (18)$$

Now, using (17), we obtain

$$|f(\xi, u, v) - f(\eta, u, v)| \leq L_1 L\delta^2. \quad (19)$$

Consider the sum of $\eta + \varepsilon f(\eta, u, v)$. Using inequality (17) and (18) we have

$$\eta + \varepsilon f(\eta, u, v) \in \xi + L\delta^2 H + \varepsilon(f(\xi, u, v) + L_1 L\delta^2 H) = \xi + \varepsilon f(\xi, u, v) + L\delta^2(1 + L_1\varepsilon).$$

Now, by virtue of condition $\xi \in \Theta^\varepsilon(M)$ we have $\eta + \varepsilon f(\eta, u, v) \in A + L\delta^2(1 + L_1\varepsilon)$.

Hence, $\eta \in \Theta^\varepsilon(A + L\delta^2(1 + L_1\varepsilon)H)$. Proof of inclusion (16) is similar to proof of the relation (15). Lemma 5 is proved.

Further, we consider only uniform partition of the segment $[0, t]$. Let $\omega_n = \{0, \varepsilon, 2\varepsilon, \dots, n\varepsilon = t\}$ be uniform partition of the segment $[0, t]$, where $\varepsilon = \frac{t}{n}$. Let $\Gamma(\varepsilon) = L\varepsilon^2 \sum_{K=1}^n (1 + L_1\varepsilon)^{k-1}$. We assume

$$\Theta^{2\varepsilon} M = \Theta^\varepsilon \Theta^\varepsilon M, \Theta^{k\varepsilon} M = \Theta^\varepsilon \Theta^{(k-1)\varepsilon} M, \Theta^{\omega_n} M = \Theta^{n\varepsilon} M,$$

$$\Theta_{2\varepsilon}M = \Theta_\varepsilon\Theta_\varepsilon M, \Theta_{k\varepsilon}M = \Theta_\varepsilon\Theta_{(k-1)\varepsilon}M, \Theta_{\omega_n}M = \Theta_{n\varepsilon}M.$$

Note that for convenience entry is similar to the notation $\Theta^{k\varepsilon}$, $\Theta_{k\varepsilon}$ introduced $A^{k\varepsilon}$, $A_{k\varepsilon}$.

Theorem 3. The following inclusions

$$A^{\omega_n}M \subset \Theta^{\omega_n}(M + \Gamma(\varepsilon)H) \subset A^{\omega_n}(M + 2\Gamma(\varepsilon)H), \tag{20}$$

$$A_{\omega_n}(M \underline{*} 2\Gamma(\varepsilon)H) \subset \Theta_{\omega_n}(M \underline{*} \Gamma(\varepsilon)H) \subset A_{\omega_n}(M) \tag{21}$$

are valid.

Proof. From Lemma 4 it follows that

$$A^\varepsilon M \subset \Theta^\varepsilon(M + L\varepsilon^2 H).$$

Using Lemma 4 again we obtain

$$A^{2\varepsilon}M \subset \Theta^\varepsilon(\Theta^\varepsilon(M + L\varepsilon^2 H) + L\varepsilon^2 H).$$

Applying Lemma 5 to the right side of this inclusion we have

$$A^{2\varepsilon}M \subset \Theta^{2\varepsilon}(M + L\varepsilon^2(1 + L_1\varepsilon)H).$$

Suppose

$$A^{p\varepsilon}M \subset \Theta^{p\varepsilon}(M + L\varepsilon^2 \sum_{k=1}^p (1 + L_1\varepsilon)^{k-1} H). \tag{22}$$

We shall show that

$$A^{(p+1)\varepsilon}M \subset \Theta^{(p+1)\varepsilon}(M + L\varepsilon^2 \sum_{k=1}^{p+1} (1 + L_1\varepsilon)^{k-1} H). \tag{23}$$

Applying Lemma 4 to the inclusion (21), we obtain

$$A^{(p+1)\varepsilon}M \subset \Theta^\varepsilon(\Theta^{p\varepsilon}(M + L\varepsilon^2 \sum_{k=1}^p (1 + L_1\varepsilon)^{k-1} H) + L\varepsilon^2).$$

Now, using Lemma 5 we have at the relation r

$$A^{(p+1)\varepsilon}M \subset \Theta^{(p+1)\varepsilon}(M + L\varepsilon^2 \sum_{k=1}^{p+1} (1 + L_1\varepsilon)^{k-1} H).$$

This implies

$$A^{n\varepsilon}M \subset \Theta^{n\varepsilon}(M + L\varepsilon^2 \sum_{k=1}^n (1 + L_1\varepsilon)^{k-1} H).$$

Consequently,

$$A^{\omega_n}M \subset \Theta^{\omega_n}(M + \Gamma(\varepsilon)H).$$

Similarly of that, the following inclusion

$$\Theta^{\omega_n}(M + \Gamma(\varepsilon)H) \subset A^{\omega_n}(M + 2\Gamma(\varepsilon)H)$$

will established.

Consequently,

$$A^{\omega_n}M \subset \Theta^{\omega_n}(M + \Gamma(\varepsilon)H) \subset A^{\omega_n}(M + 2\Gamma(\varepsilon)H).$$

Theorem 3 is proved.

Theorem 4. The following equality holds

$$\Pi^t M = \bigcup_{\delta > 0} \Theta^t(M + \delta H), \quad (24)$$

for $M \in C(R^d)$,

$$\Pi_t M = \bigcup_{\delta > 0} \Theta_t(M \underline{*} \delta H), \quad (25)$$

for open M , $M \subset R^d$.

Proof. Consider the value of $\Gamma(\varepsilon) = L\varepsilon^2 \sum_{k=1}^n (1 + L_1\varepsilon)^k$. It is easy to see that $\Gamma(\varepsilon) \leq \varepsilon L(e^{L_1\theta} - 1)$. By choose of partitions we have $\Gamma(\varepsilon) \leq \varepsilon L(e^{L\theta} - 1) < \delta$, i.e. $\varepsilon < \frac{\delta}{L(e^{L_1\theta} - 1)}$. Inclusion (19) implies

$$A^{\omega_n} M \subset \Theta^{\omega_n}(M + \delta H) \subset A^{\omega_n}(M + 2\delta H).$$

Transition to the intersection on the ω_n in these relations term by term, we have

$$A^t M \subset \bigcap_{\omega_n} \Theta^{\omega_n}(M + \delta H) \subset \bigcup_{\omega} A^{\omega}(M + 2\delta H).$$

Now taking into account Lemma 1 we obtain,

$$A^t M \subset \Theta^t(M + \delta H) \subset A^t(M + 2\delta H).$$

Since $\delta > 0$ is arbitrary we have

$$A^t M \subset \bigcap_{\delta > 0} \Theta^t(M + \delta H) \subset \bigcap_{\delta > 0} A^t(M + 2\delta H).$$

Now, Theorem 1 and Theorem 2 imply

$$\Pi^t M = \bigcap_{\delta > 0} \Theta^t(M + \delta H).$$

The proof of the equality (24) is similar to the proof of (23). Theorem 4 is proved.

4 The connection between the upper and lower operators and its application to the nonlinear differential games of pursuit with fixed time

We shall study connection between operators Π^t and Π_t .

Theorem 5. For any $\delta > 0$, there exists a number ε , for all $|\omega_n| < \varepsilon$ the inclusions are valid

$$\Theta^{\omega_n} M \subset \Theta_{\omega_n}(M + \delta H), \quad (26)$$

$$\Theta^{\omega_n}(M \underline{*} \delta H) \subset \Theta_{\omega_n} M. \quad (27)$$

The proofs are analogous, so we confine ourselves to the proof of (25). For convenience, we consider the operator $\Theta^{3\varepsilon}$. By definition

$$\Theta^{3\varepsilon} M = \bigcap_{v \in Q} \bigcup_{u \in P} \{\xi_1 \in R^d \mid z(\varepsilon, u, v, \xi_1) = \xi_1 + \varepsilon f(\xi_1, u, v) \in \Theta^{2\varepsilon} M.\}$$

Furthermore,

$$\Theta^{3\varepsilon}M \subset \bigcup_{u \in P} \bigcap_{v \in Q} \{\xi_1 \in R^d \mid \xi_1 + \varepsilon f(\xi_1, u, v) \in \bigcup_{u \in P} [\Theta^{2\varepsilon}M - \varepsilon f(\xi_1, u, v)] + K\varepsilon H\}.$$

Here we considered the fact $\varepsilon f(\xi_1, u, v) \subset K\varepsilon H$.

By repeating this process with respect to $\Theta^{2\varepsilon}$ and Θ^ε we get

$$\begin{aligned} \Theta^{3\varepsilon}M &\subset \bigcup_{u \in P} \bigcap_{v \in Q} \{\xi_1 \in R^d \mid \xi_1 + \varepsilon f(\xi_1, u, v) \in \bigcup_{u \in P} \bigcap_{v \in Q} \{\xi_2 \in R^d \mid \xi_2 \in \\ &\in \bigcup_{u \in P} [\bigcap_{v \in Q} [\xi_3 \in R^d \mid \xi_3 \in \bigcup_{u \in P} [M - \varepsilon f(\xi_3, u, v)] - \varepsilon f(\xi_2, u, v)] - \varepsilon f(\xi_1, u, v)] + K\varepsilon H\}. \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

Note that $\xi_{i+1} = \xi_i + \varepsilon f(\xi_i, u, v)$. Therefore, in virtue of the condition A, we have $|f(\xi_{i+1}, u, v) - f(\xi_i, u, v)| \leq L_1 |\xi_{i+1} - \xi_i| \leq L_1 K\varepsilon H = L\varepsilon H$, where $L = L_1 K$. This implies $\varepsilon f(\xi_{i+1}, u, v) \subset \varepsilon f(\xi_i, u, v) + L\varepsilon^2$, $\varepsilon f(\xi_i, u, v) \subset \varepsilon f(\xi_{i+1}, u, v) + L\varepsilon^2$.

Taking into account of these relations, we replace any vector $\varepsilon f(\xi_i, u, v)$ in the right side of the inclusions (27) on $\varepsilon f(\xi_{i+1}, u, v) + L\varepsilon^2$ for $i = 1, 2$ and using the inclusion (4) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \Theta^{3\varepsilon}M &\subset \bigcup_{u \in P} \bigcap_{v \in Q} \{\xi_1 \in R^d \mid \xi_1 + \varepsilon f(\xi_1, u, v) \in \bigcup_{u \in P} \bigcap_{v \in Q} [\xi_2 \in R^d \mid \xi_2 \in \\ &\in \bigcup_{u \in P} \bigcap_{v \in Q} [\xi_3 \in R^d \mid \xi_3 \in [M - \varepsilon f(\xi_3, u, v) + L\varepsilon^2 + K\varepsilon H]] - \varepsilon f(\xi_2, u, v) + \\ &\quad + L\varepsilon^2] + K\varepsilon H\}. \end{aligned}$$

This implies,

$$\begin{aligned} \Theta^{3\varepsilon}M &\subset \bigcup_{u \in P} \bigcap_{v \in Q} \{\xi_1 \in R^d \mid \xi_1 + \varepsilon f(\xi_1, u, v) \in \bigcup_{u \in P} \bigcap_{v \in Q} [\xi_2 \in R^d \mid \xi_2 + \varepsilon f(\xi_2, u, v) \in \\ &\in \bigcup_{u \in P} \bigcap_{v \in Q} [\xi_3 \in R^d \mid \xi_3 + \varepsilon f(\xi_3, u, v) \in [M + L\varepsilon^2 + K\varepsilon H]] + L\varepsilon^2] + K\varepsilon H\}. \end{aligned}$$

Consequently,

$$\Theta^{3\varepsilon}M \subset \Theta_\varepsilon(\Theta_\varepsilon(\Theta_\varepsilon(M + L\varepsilon^2H + K\varepsilon H) + L\varepsilon^2H) + K\varepsilon H). \quad (29)$$

Now, applying Lemma 5 to the right side of the inclusion (28) we have

$$\Theta^{3\varepsilon}M \subset \Theta_{3\varepsilon}(M + L\varepsilon^2H + K\varepsilon H + L\varepsilon^2(1 + L_1\varepsilon)H + K\varepsilon(1 + L_1\varepsilon)^2H)$$

i.e.

$$\Theta^{3\varepsilon}M \subset \Theta_{3\varepsilon}(M + (L\varepsilon^2 \sum_{k=1}^2 (1 + L_1\varepsilon)^{k-1} + K\varepsilon(1 + (1 + L_1\varepsilon)^2))H)$$

Repeating this process one more time we obtain

$$\Theta^{n\varepsilon}M \subset \Theta_{n\varepsilon}(M + \Gamma(\varepsilon)H), \quad (30)$$

where

$$\Gamma(\varepsilon) = L\varepsilon^2 \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (1 + L_1\varepsilon)^{k-1} + K\varepsilon(1 + (1 + L_1\varepsilon)^{n-1}).$$

To complete the proof of Theorem 5 it suffices to choose $\varepsilon > 0$ satisfying the inequality $\Gamma(\varepsilon) < \delta$, as it was done in the proof of Theorem 4.

Therefore, for all $|\omega_n| < \varepsilon$ the inclusion

$$\Theta^{\omega_n} M \subset \Theta_{\omega_n}(M + \delta H)$$

holds. Theorem 5 is proved.

Theorem 6. The following equality holds

$$\Pi^t M = \bigcap_{\delta > 0} \Pi_t(M + \delta H), \tag{31}$$

for $M \in C(R^d)$ and

$$\Pi_t M = \bigcup_{\delta > 0} \Pi^t(M_{\underline{*}\delta H}) \tag{32}$$

for open M , $M \subset R^d$.

Proof. From Theorem 5 it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi^{\omega_n} M &\subset \Theta^{\omega_n}(M + \delta H) \subset \Theta_{\omega_n}(M + 2\delta H) \subset \\ &\subset \Pi_{\omega_n}(M + 3\delta H). \end{aligned}$$

This implies that for any $\delta > 0$, there exists a number $\varepsilon > 0$ for all ω_n , such that $|\omega_n| < \varepsilon$ the relation

$$\Pi^{\omega_n} M \subset \Pi_{\omega_n}(M + 3\delta H).$$

Hence, by Lemma 3, we have

$$\Pi^t M \subset \bigcap_{\delta > 0} \Pi_t(M + 3\delta H).$$

On the other hand,

$$\bigcap_{\delta > 0} \Pi_t(M + 3\delta H) \subset \bigcap_{\delta > 0} \Pi^t(M + 3\delta H).$$

Now, using the first part of Theorem 1, we have

$$\bigcap_{\delta > 0} \Pi_t(M + 3\delta H) \subset \Pi^t M.$$

Hence, we obtain the equality (30). The proof of the equality (31) is similar to the proof of (30).

Theorem 6 is proved.

Applications of upper and lower operators to nonlinear differential games is similarly to the linear case[2,4,10-13,19]. Therefore, we confine ourselves to a brief presentation of the definitions of basic concepts and to state basic results in connection with the system(1).

In further for brevity entry we assume $P(\varepsilon) = P[0, \varepsilon]$ and $Q(\varepsilon) = Q[0, \varepsilon]$.

Definition 5. The mapping $V_\varepsilon^* : R^d \rightarrow Q(\varepsilon)$ is said to be ε - strategy of the evader in the upper game. The mapping $U_\varepsilon^* : R^d \times Q(\varepsilon) \rightarrow P(\varepsilon)$ is said to be ε -strategy of the pursuer in the upper game.

Definition 6. The mapping $U_*^\varepsilon : R^d \rightarrow P(\varepsilon)$ is said to be ε - strategy of the pursuer in the lower game. The mapping $V_*^\varepsilon : R^d \times P(\varepsilon) \rightarrow Q(\varepsilon)$ is said to be ε -strategy of the evader in the lower game.

A given initial point z_0 and a given pair of strategies $U_\varepsilon^*, V_\varepsilon^*$ give rise to a unique trajectory $z(t) = z(t, z_0, U_\varepsilon^*, V_\varepsilon^*)$, $t \geq 0$. This trajectory is defined on $[0, \varepsilon]$ as solution of the Cauchy problem

$$\frac{dz}{dt} = f(z(t), u_0(t), v_0(t)), z(0) = z_0,$$

where $v_0(\cdot) = V_\varepsilon^*(z_0)$ and $u_0(\cdot) = U_\varepsilon^*(z_0, v_0(\cdot))$

The trajectory is then extended from $[0, k\varepsilon]$ to $[0, (k+1)\varepsilon]$ as the solution Cauchy problem

$$\frac{dz}{dt} = f(z(t), u_k(t), v_k(t)), z(k\varepsilon + 0) = z(k\varepsilon - 0),$$

where $v_k(t) = v(t - k\varepsilon)$, $v(\cdot) = V_\varepsilon^*(z(k\varepsilon))$ and $u_k(t) = U_\varepsilon^*(z_k\varepsilon, v(\cdot))(t - k\varepsilon)$, $t \in [k\varepsilon, (k+1)\varepsilon]$.

The trajectory $z(t) = z(t, z_0, U_\varepsilon^*, V_\varepsilon^*)$ corresponding to a given initial point z_0 and a given pair of strategies $U_\varepsilon^*, V_\varepsilon^*$ is defined similarly.

Definition 7. Pursuit from the point z_0 can be completed at the time τ in the upper game if for any $\varepsilon = \frac{\tau}{n}$, there exists ε -strategy of the pursuer U_ε^* such that $z(\tau) = z(\tau, z_0, U_\varepsilon^*, V_\varepsilon^*) \in M$ for any ε -strategy of the evader V_ε^* .

Concept of possibility to complete pursuit at the time τ in the lower game can be introduced similarly.

On the base of these definitions, the equality (30) in Theorem 6 can be interpreted as follows. If $M \in C(R^d)$, then pursuit from a point z_0 can be completed at the time τ in the upper game if and only if the pursuer in the lower game can transfer the phase point from the initial point z_0 into any neighborhood of the terminal set at the time τ (see [2,3,10,12,21-22])

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